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MODERN APPROACHES TO TEACHING THE HITTITE LANGUAGE.

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Anatasia:

Methods of learning a foreign language, as well as their application methods and level of efficiency. Analysis of new pedagogical requirements and applied processes.

Key words: Game activity, language learning requirements, competence.

Interest in learning foreign languages has increased significantly this year. This is also caused by the decree measures aimed at the development of foreign languages after the independence of our country. The educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded person. Also, the presidential law on measures to teach foreign languages, adopted on December 10, 2012, expands opportunities for learning foreign languages. New methods and requirements for the assessment of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers in our country have been developed in accordance with the European recommendations "CEFR". Today, the ability to know foreign languages is becoming one of the integral parts of the education system. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, their demand for language learning is high. Modern In society, foreign languages are becoming an important component of any professional education. Among the above-mentioned, they learn by getting acquainted with educational courses or independent sets that help to learn a foreign language. Today, different levels of language knowledge There are large collections of educational materials for those with disabilities. Success in achieving this goal depends on the practical methods and skills of teachers. The ability to use information technologies and modern teaching methods helps to quickly understand new materials.

1. By combining various methods, the teacher will be able to solve specific educational programs. In this regard, teachers and students should familiarize themselves with modern teaching methods. It is formed. In this, one of the methods of teaching and learning gives an effective and efficient result.

2. As time progresses, new processes are increasing in every field. Different methods are also appearing in language learning. .Teaching at the personal life stage of

such students, teaching at the middle stage, teaching according to the above teaching. A special program is developed by the teacher for each stage.

Pronunciation is important at the initial stage. Harmer says that "pronunciation is the first requirement of native speakers during conversation." , if the speaker's pronunciation is wrong, all this is useless. Native speakers can understand what the speaker's purpose is even with grammatical errors if the speaker pronounces the words correctly. In the middle stage of learning English, the focus is more on the size of the texts and the It is necessary to use methods that help to increase thinking, speech activity, and initiative in understanding the language. Sufficient attention should be paid to the formation of speech skills and the development of social flexibility in trainings during the educational process. In addition, the success of each lesson in education depends on It depends on the proper organization of training. The lesson should be based on the creative cooperation of the teacher and the student. Only then will the students be able to think independently and freely, and will be educated. It is known that the lesson is conducted on the basis of various games, it helps to demonstrate the possibilities of students, to concentrate, to increase their knowledge and skills, and to increase their competence in language learning. In the process of games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a regular lesson and works freely. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach students to think independently.

Speak" method is more convenient for teaching English to students. helps to develop oral speech of students, for this he uses pictures related to the topic. "Question Potatoes" - "Quiz Cards" potatoes are distributed according to the number of students and allows all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves time. Each innovative technology has its own advantages. Nowadays, knowledge of a foreign language is of great importance, and the following method is also effective in learning it, that is, watching English-language movies and films with imitation and showing them in oral speech.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the effectiveness of any methods and approaches is evaluated by the ability to express the correct opinion on the aspirations and process of both parties, that is, students and teachers.

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